

The Effects of Stress and Flow Velocity on Corrosion Behavior of Vinyl Ester Resin and Glass Composites

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ABSTRACT

The effect of stress and flow velocity on corrosion behavior of mainly vinyl ester resin and its glass composites were studied by immersion tests under no loading, creep-rupture tests, pipe flow and rotating-bar corrosion tests in water, NaOH and HCl solutions at 50°C. The degradation was evaluated by change of weight, retention of strength, change of absorbance in IR spectrum, total organic carbon and optical or scanning electron microscopic observation.

It was found that stress and flow velocity accelerated the degradation of materials, and stress effect was more clear in composites compared with the resin.

Therefore a conventional immersion test is not always sufficient to evaluate the corrosion behavior of the materials.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics have been widely used in industry as materials for chemical and pollution control equipments because of their high resistance to chemical attack and high strength.

There are many reports concerning the chemical resistance of resins and composites, and these are almost based on simple immersion test (1-5). It is not sufficient to design the corrosion resistant equipments according to simple immersion test only. For example in case of large storage tank, pipe and high-temperature equipment system, it will be necessary to consider the effect of stress, flow velocity and temperature gradient respectively in design (6-9).

In this paper, creep-rupture tests in corrosive liquids and corrosion tests by flowing liquids besides simple immersion tests were made for both resin and composites to clarify the effect of stress and flow velocity on the corrosion behavior.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous solutions used as corrosive environments were pure water, HCl and NaOH.

Immersion tests were made up to 5000 hours in three environments at 50°C. After immersion, tensile or flexural test was performed in air at room temperature, and the degree of degradation was evaluated in terms of retention of strength.

Creep-rupture tests in corrosive environments were performed using ASTM D638-76 type tensile specimens under very low flow rate of lcc/min.

Tests under flowing conditions were performed by both pipe flow and rotating-bar methods at 50°C. Schematic view of test apparatus is shown in Fig.1. In rotating-bar test, hollow cylindrical specimen with a outer diameter 30mm, a thickness 2mm and a length 60mm was rotated in liquid. The retention of flexural strength was measured by specimen of 3mm width cut from the cylindrical specimen.

In pipe flow method, rectangular shaped flexural test specimen with a width 25mm, a thickness 2mm and a length 60mm was installed at the center of pipe. After testing flexural test was made according to ASTM D790-71.

Besides strength, measurements of weight change and total organic carbon (TOC), analyses by infrared spectroscopy and X-ray microanalyzer and also observation with optical and scanning electron microscope were made to investigate the degradation behaviors.

The materials tested were novorak type vinyl-ester resin (Derakane 470-45) and E-glass mat reinforced vinyl ester composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IMMERSION TEST

Change of weight. Fig.2 shows the weight change of the resin tested in three environments. In case of water, weight of specimen increases with increasing immersion time, and then it tends to approach the equilibrium state. In NaOH solution, equilibrium is observed after about 100 or 200 hours, beyond this region the weight begins to increase again, and then decreases abruptly. As a result of hydrolysis reaction of the resin by corrosive liquid, small cracks are formed which promotes the penetration of liquid, and low molecular weight components existed before immersion and also produced by hydrolysis are dissolved into liquid. Fig.3 shows the optical micrographs of specimen surfaces in which initiation and growth of cracks can be recognized clearly corresponding to the results shown in Fig.2.

The effect of NaOH concentration shown in Fig.2 can be explained by the ability of wetting of liquid to resin and the corrosivity of liquid. The contact angle of liquid for resin increases with increase of concentration of liquid up to 30 wt.% as shown in Fig.4, and the corrosivity of liquid also increases with concentration.

Fig.5 shows the results of weight change for composites(G.C. 60 wt.%) and the behaviors in water and NaOH solution are similar to those of the resin(Fig.2), while in HCl the weight decreases remarkably immediately after immersion by the severe chemical attack.

Change of mechanical strength. Fig.6 presents the retention of flexural strength of the resin. The decrease in strength is slight in water even after long time immersion, however, it is very distinct in NaOH after several hundred hours because of the generation of small cracks caused by hydrolysis of ester group.

EFFECT OF STRESS

Fig.7 shows the result of creep-rupture test for composites(G.C. 60 wt.%) in three environments. Solid lines show result of creep-rupture test and dotted lines show those of simple immersion test. The ordinate are ratio of applied stress to tensile strength before testing for creep-rupture test and retention of tensile strength for immersion test.

In HCl and NaOH, the behavior of degradation consists of three linear stages and the gradient of each stage becomes same for both test results. This suggests that the degradation mechanism is same for both tests, but the second stage is recognized from the earlier stage of creep than simple immersion. Therefore, the stress shortens the transition time from the first degradation stage to the second one and also from the second to the third. Moreover, the degradation occurs more severely in HCl than in NaOH under loading.

Fig.8 shows the creep-rupture curves of composites with various glass contents tested in NaOH solution. The effect of glass content is clearly seen and especially remarkable in the second stage, and in case of resin only the first degradation stage is recognized. This suggests that the first stage is dominated by the degradation of resin, on the contrary, the second one is dominated by that of glass-resin interface and/or glass fiber.

More clear effect of stress is shown in Fig.9. Tensile strength of composites was measured at room temperature in air after interrupting creep-rupture test at some intervals. The result shows that stress accelerates corrosion of the material, and the higher the stress the shorter the transition time.

EFFECT OF FLOW VELOCITY

Pipe flow method. Figs.10 and 11 show the effect of Reynolds number on weight change and retention of flexural strength of the resin for 25wt.% NaOH solution. In flowing liquid, weight gain is higher than that of immersion test from about 50 hours, and then decreases gradually from about 500 hours. Fig. 12 shows the relationship between results of weight change and retention of flexural strength in 25wt.% NaOH obtained by replotting Figs. 10 and 11. Very close correlations was obtained in each region which is prominent physical or chemical degradation, however, the behaviors in immersion and flowing condition show different tendency.

In Figs.10 and 11, the effect of flow velocity on weight change and retention of strength is not obvious, but effect of flow velocity was clearly found in observation of specimen surface by scanning electron microscope and measurement of surface roughness. Fig.13 shows that the surface roughness increases with increasing testing time and Reynolds number.

We have shown in infrared study previously that ester group decreases and on the contrary carboxylate group increases during immersion testing owing to hydrolytic corrosion (7-9). Then the effect of Reynolds number on absorbance in infrared spectrum for both groups were investigated as shown in Fig.14. The variation of absorbance becomes sharper with increase of Reynolds number and testing time. This means that hydrolysis occurs more easily at high Reynolds number.

In case of water, though the test was carried out for long period and at high Reynolds number, the effect of flow velocity on strength change was almost negligible because of very slight chemical degradation.

Rotating-bar method. Fig.15 shows the variation of the retention of flexural strength for the resin in 25wt.% NaOH tested by rotating-bar method. Comparing with the results of pipe flow method shown in Fig.11, the degree of degradation in this method is more mild than that in the pipe. The strengths in Fig.15 were measured with specimens dried for one day after removal from liquid. Fig.16 shows the measurements of strength after 30 days of drying in desiccator. As liquid penetrated into resin is almost removed out, the strength is recovered to its initial level except that for a long testing time and high Reynolds number. This suggests that the degradation in short testing time and low Reynolds number is mainly due to the physical degradation such as swelling by liquid penetration, while for a long testing time and high Reynolds number the chemical degradation becomes prominent.

As the measured weight change reveals only apparent behavior, distinct effect of Reynolds number on weight change was not observed. Then the amount of dissolved organic carbon was measured by means of total organic carbon analyzer in 25wt.% NaOH solution as shown in Fig.17. The dissolution of resin is accelerated under flowing condition, therefore it is found that the amount of penetration of liquid into resin is also accelerated under flowing condition.

Figs.18 and 19 show the results of weight change and retention of flexural strength for composites in 10wt.% NaOH solution. The difference between results of immersion and rotating condition in both figures can not be seen within these testing time. However, in composites the weight change was higher than that

of resin, and decrease in retention of strength was recognized remarkably even in immersion tests. This implies that the glass-resin interface plays an important role for the degradation of composites.

In HCl solution, as the dissolution of resin measured by TOC was lower than that in NaOH solution (8,9), it is supposed that the weight change depends mainly on the amount of liquid penetration. So the role of the amount of liquid penetration to the weight change is considered to be larger than that in NaOH solution, and the effect of Reynolds number on the weight change will be more clear. Fig.20 shows results of weight change in HCl solution, and distinct effect of Reynolds number is observed. As the weight change is summation of the amount of penetrated liquid and dissolution of resin, it is necessary to clarify the behavior of these two factors in order to understand the degradation mechanism. The penetrated liquid into resin at various Reynolds numbers were investigated by means of X-ray microanalyzer with respect to chlorine ions as shown in Fig.21. It is found that the penetrated chlorine ions increase with an increase of Reynolds number which coincides with the results of Fig.20. The differences in the behaviors of degradation between HCl and NaOH are due to the difference in mechanism of hydrolysis reaction in each environments. Hydrolysis reaction of ester in HCl is reversible, and chemical degradation is restricted at or near the specimen surface (7-9). Therefore, though the effect of flowing condition on degradation of composites was not clear in NaOH (Fig.19), it is expected that the effect will be more remarkable in HCl.

CONCLUSION

The effect of stress and flow velocity on degradation of vinyl ester resin and its glass composites were investigated. It was found that both stress and flow velocity accelerated the corrosion of these materials, and this tendency is more prominent in glass composites compared to resin. Therefore a simple immersion test is not always sufficient to evaluate the corrosion behavior of these materials.

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Fig.1 Schematic view of testing apparatus. (a) rotating-bar test, (b) pipe flow test

Fig.2 Weight change of vinyl ester resin exposed to various environments.

Fig.4 Variation of contact angles of NaOH solution with concentration.

Fig.3 Optical micrographs of specimen surfaces exposed to 25wt.% NaOH.

Fig.5 Weight change of composites (G.C. 60wt.%) in various environments.

Fig.7 Correlation between immersion test and creep-rupture test for composites (G.C. 60wt.%).

Fig.9 Effect of stress on degradation of composites in 10wt.% NaOH.

Fig.6 Retention of flexural strength of resin in various environments.

Fig.8 Creep-rupture curves of composites with various glass contents.

Fig.10 Weight change of resin tested by pipe flow method in 25wt.% NaOH.

Fig. 11 Retention of flexural strength of resin tested by pipe flow method in 25wt.% NaOH.

Fig. 12 Correlation between retention of strength and weight change in immersion and pipe flow tests.

Fig. 13 Variation of surface roughness with testing time and Reynolds number.

Fig. 14 Variation of ester and carboxylate peak ratios of resin tested by pipe method with exposure time.

Fig. 15 Retention of flexural strength of resin tested by rotating-bar method in 25wt.% NaOH.

Fig. 16 Retention of flexural strength of resin after drying.

Fig. 17 Effect of flowing condition on dissolved total organic carbon from resin in 25wt.% NaOH.

Fig. 18 Weight change of composites (G.C. 35wt.%) tested by rotating-bar method in 10wt.% NaOH.

Fig. 19 Retention of flexural strength of composites (G.C. 35wt.%) tested by rotating-bar method in 10wt.% NaOH.

Fig. 20 Weight change of resin in 22.8 wt.% HCl.

Fig. 21 Penetration of chlorine ion into resin measured by X-ray microanalyzer.